

UKSSDC Data Prioritisation Survey

1. Introduction

The UK Solar System Data Centre is in the process of integration with the other NERC data centres hosted at Rutherford Appleton Laboratory.

We would be grateful to both current and potential archive users if you would complete this user survey which seeks to find out how well you think the UKSSDC is performing and how important its constituent datasets are likely to be for your future research.

Users may respond anonymously if they wish - although it is useful for us to be able to respond to issues.

The questionnaire should take no more than 10 minutes to complete.

2. About You

1. Your contact details are not required, but may be helpful to us in understanding the results or in following up any specific comments.

Name:

Institution:

Email Address:

2. What is your interest in UKSSDC data?

- Research scientist
- Other professional (please comment below)
- Radio amateur
- Other private interest (please comment below)

Comments

3. Do any of these agencies fund your work?

- Natural Environment Research Council
- Science and Technology Facilities Council
- UK Space Agency
- Other (please specify)

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4. Before being asked to complete this survey, were you aware of the UK Solar System Data Centre (UKSSDC) or the World Data Centre for Solar-Terrestrial Physics, Chilton (WDC for STP, Chilton)?

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

3. Data holdings - Online

1. Please tell us what you think about these datasets, available online from the UKSSDC:

	Have you ever used this dataset?	Did you know it was available?	Might you use it in the future?
Scaled ionospheric parameters	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Prompt ionospheric data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ionograms	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Geomagnetic indices	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Auroral Oval Indicator plots	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Solar indices	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sunspot group reports	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
IMF and solar wind parameters	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
SOHO	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
TRACE	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
STEREO	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
CHIANTI	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (please specify in comments box)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Any comments?

4. Data Holdings - Offline

The UKSSDC holds a wide range of data on physical media, which we would like to make more available to users.

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1. Please tell us about your knowledge/usage of the UKSSDC physical archive.

Have you ever used this dataset? Did you know it was available? Might you use it in the future?

Paper ionograms	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Film ionograms	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ionospheric scaled parameter bulletins	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Solar Images (Ca K and Ph)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Royal Observatory Greenwich Photo-heliographic Results	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Riometer trace recordings	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Alouette II sounder traces	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AMPTE slides	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Viking summary data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Geomagnetic indices reports	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (please specify in comments box)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Any comments?

5. Tools and Services

The UKSSDC provides a number of tools and services to users, mainly through its website. We would like know how well known and useful they are.

1. Please tell us what you think about these tools and services.

Have you ever used this service? Did you know it was available? Might you use it in the future?

Summary data plots on one page	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
MSIS model	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Coordinate Conversion tool	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Daily reports and alerts on the web	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Daily reports and alerts by email	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Monthly reports on the web	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Monthly reports by email or post	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (please specify in the comments box)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Any comments?

6. Alternative Data Sources

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1. Do you use any other data services which provide similar/comparable data products? If you do, you will be asked for more details on the next page.

- Yes
- No

7. Details of Alternative Data Sources

You have answered that you know of alternative services which provide similar/comparable data products to those from the UKSSDC.

1. Please tell us the names of these data services and which data they provide.

2. If you have used these alternative data services, can you say why you used them in preference to the UKSSDC/WDC?

- Did not know of UKSSDC/WDC
- Did not know UKSSDC/WDC held the data
- Easier to use alternative service

Other (please specify)

8. Other Solar System Data

1. Do you know of other UK Solar System science datasets that you feel should be archived in the UKSSDC?

- Yes
- No

9. Details of other Solar System Data

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1. Please provide details and contact information for the datasets you feel should be archived with the UKSSDC.

10. Support from the UKSSDC

1. Are you satisfied with the support from the UKSSDC?

- Highly satisfied
- Moderately satisfied
- Slightly satisfied
- Moderately satisfied
- Highly dissatisfied
- Don't know/not sure

2. Please add any comments, compliments or criticisms relating to the UKSSDC here:

11. Thank You

Thank you for your time spent completing this survey. Your help is much appreciated.